

FEATURES OF SOCIAL INITIATIVENESS OF A LEADER IN THE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM IN MODERN SOCIETY

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ABSTRACT

This article is devoted to the study of the features of the social initiative of managers in the management system in modern society. Social initiative is considered as an important criterion in determining not only the leader's activities within the organization, but also their contribution to the development of society. The article examines the initiative potential of a leader, creative abilities, the level of innovative decision-making, and sensitivity to the social needs of society as the main characteristics. Also, from a scientific point of view, the inseparable connection of managers' social initiative with their leadership style, communicative strategies, and motivational mechanisms in the organization is analyzed. Managers with a high level of social initiative play a leading role in the effective implementation of the organization's social obligations, the development of strong ties with employees and society, and the promotion of innovative initiatives. At the same time, the article provides recommendations aimed at increasing the social initiative of managers in the modern management system.

Introduction

In the New Republic of Uzbekistan, the large-scale and rapid reforms being implemented in the construction of the state and society require a fundamentally new approach to governance and impose an increased sense of responsibility. The strict requirements placed on leadership personality have a programmatic character, emphasizing that the development of the state and society largely depends on the effectiveness of leaders' activities. In a civilized society, a leader must stand out through high spirituality, moral integrity, dedication, faith, patriotism, and exceptional competence. In our view, the requirements set by the President for senior officials are directly applicable to mid-level managerial personnel as well.

Today's leader or manager must differ sharply from predecessors in terms of socio-spiritual and socio-psychological structure. Only an inquisitive, entrepreneurial, competent, and self-sacrificing leader can adapt successfully to the conditions of a market economy. A manager who waits for instructions from higher authorities and is dominated by a dependency-oriented mentality will be unable to function effectively as a leader [1, p. 348].

Regardless of individuals' social status—whether employee or manager—internal and external factors shaping their labor activity always exist. The emergence, scope, and positive or negative impact of these factors depend on the individual's personality as well as their colleagues, team members, and employees. The reality is that from birth until reaching a certain social status, individuals demonstrate in their daily behavior the characteristics, intellectual skills, and knowledge they have acquired at various stages of development. From this perspective, primary attention is consistently focused on the activity of the leader's personality [2, p. 126].

The authority of a managerial leader is manifested in their ability to demonstrate stable willpower in every action and activity. In interpersonal relations, authority fosters mutual understanding, enables accurate perception of individuals by others, shapes individual leadership style, and serves as a factor of production efficiency as well as a mechanism for creating a positive psychological climate. The following requirements are imposed on a leader's willpower:

- concentration of volitional strength;
- perseverance and determination in achieving goals despite managerial challenges;
- initiative, independence, and creativity;
- courage, decisiveness, and disregard for obstacles;
- composure, emotional stability, and self-control;
- discipline, self-management, and responsibility, among others [3, pp. 100–101].

As described, these requirements form the basis for subjective effectiveness in activity and for establishing a favorable psychological environment. Why is a single trait considered as an entire mechanism of activity? The reason is that within the framework of activity, alongside willpower, a sense of duty, responsibility, and self-confidence gradually increases. These qualities manifest differently among various leaders. In the management process, issues related to the identification and development of such qualities and approaches are addressed. As emphasized, including psychological knowledge and mental state as key influencing factors has a solid scientific basis and is beneficial both for the management process and for leader–employee relations [4, pp. 145–146].

When analyzing modern management styles, the natural question arises: “Which style is better?” In response, it should be noted that a leader must stand above styles—able to observe them from a higher perspective and select and apply the most appropriate one according to the situation. Thus, the essence of modern management mastery lies in ensuring the team's commitment to achieving common goals. At the same time, a leader should always remain a good friend to their employees.

Weaknesses in leadership skills pose serious challenges. Leadership represents a complex system of interconnected interpersonal relations that must be purposefully organized. In addition to managerial responsibilities, leaders are required to perform functions ranging from financial management to educational guidance, which necessitates specific professional competencies. The lack of such competencies significantly complicates leadership effectiveness.

The absence of systematic management training, mentoring, and instructional guidance negatively affects organizational development. Ensuring enterprise growth largely

depends on personnel training and professional development, equipping employees with essential knowledge and skills. This issue is reflected in the “National Program for Personnel Training” [5, pp. 145–146]. If a leader fails to transfer experience to younger generations, the principle of succession is violated; failure to develop necessary competencies leads to short-sighted approaches to future development, while neglecting knowledge transfer makes sustainable progress impossible.

A low level of ability to unite the workforce is another critical shortcoming. A psychologically healthy team environment embodies stable emotional elements such as mutual support, friendship, compatibility, harmony, solidarity, understanding, and sympathy. Collective opinion, group aspiration, collective consciousness, shared thinking, and interpersonal compatibility constitute integral components of the psychological climate.

Inability to attract others through innovation further weakens leadership effectiveness. Although a leader may generate new ideas and set specific goals, failure to inspire and engage others reflects poor management skills. In this context, leaders should not hesitate to engage in self-presentation or “self-promotion.”

Deficiencies in communication skills, including lack of friendliness, modesty, and politeness, also hinder leadership effectiveness. By possessing ethnopsychological awareness, a leader can develop these qualities. Achieving goals becomes possible through the cultivation of national identity, national consciousness, national character, national emotions, and culturally grounded interpersonal relations.

Weakness in intellect and insight represents another limitation. During the appointment or promotion of leaders, intellectual capacity and perceptiveness must be taken into account, as an effective leader constitutes nearly 50% of an organization’s strength. Therefore, emphasizing knowledgeability, talent, intelligence, and wisdom as essential leadership qualities is highly justified [6, pp. 78–79].

A modern leader must be business-oriented, efficient, deep-thinking, and extremely attentive. Achieving tangible results is impossible without the ability to respond swiftly to unexpected changes. Only individuals capable of adapting to market economy conditions and possessing marketing-oriented thinking can successfully fulfill leadership roles. Weakness in these abilities indicates the absence of real managerial capacity. Successfully overcoming any situation requires strong business acumen.

Deficiencies in leadership activity and ways to eliminate them.

Analysis of materials collected in recent years indicates the existence of several shortcomings in leadership practices. One major issue is the inability to practice self-management. A leader who cannot plan activities, exercise self-control, conduct self-assessment, issue self-directed instructions, engage in self-improvement, or effectively utilize intellectual and physical resources is ultimately unable to manage themselves.

Insufficient understanding of the characteristics of managerial activity and the inability to adequately comprehend them within one’s cognitive framework significantly undermines effective governance. Management activity is highly complex, encompassing financial, economic, ideological, legal, and educational dimensions. It also performs a number of functions, reflecting relationships such as “human–human,” “human–technology,” “human–nature,” and “human–prestige.” A leader achieves professional advancement by mastering

each aspect and function of managerial activity at a high level. However, failure to comprehend one or another dimension may result in organizational dysfunction, artificial stagnation, and operational inefficiency within an enterprise.

A lack of understanding damages the management process itself, as the leader's cognitive capacity fails to accommodate these elements, leading to disruptions in governance. The breakdown of internal coherence among managerial components and reliance on "trial-and-error" approaches can produce negative consequences. In the context of globalization, making critical decisions and managing teams effectively are directly dependent on the leader's specific psychological characteristics. In this regard, the role of a leader's image in the process of activity serves as a crucial factor in ensuring overall effectiveness [7, p. 62].

A leader's image refers to the individual's distinctive internal and external characteristics. In contemporary conditions, a leader must be both a competent specialist and a genuine entrepreneur, an effective organizer who is also aware of their rights and capable of using time efficiently. Indeed, the way we utilize the present determines how the future will, in turn, shape us

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